

Automation of Sub-Processes in the Design Stage

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Abstract

The dissertation addresses the role of automation in the Design Stage of BIM. The large use of BIM and the desire to respond more effectively to the construction requirements have diffused the development of software, plug-ins, add-ons, and Programming Languages scripts. This study evaluates the current developments in this field, its applications, and its usability based on sub-processes that were identified as potential for being automated.

The thesis is organized into 5 chapters. The first provides an introduction to the topic, and the second a literature review about the design stage, the deliverables in this stage, the currently available automation in this stage, and how is possible to develop new ones. The third chapter is the survey of the sub-processes that are going to be automated in this work and how they were solved. The fourth chapter illustrates a case study with a list of tasks to do, manually and with automation, based on the sub-processes and the results of this case study. The final chapter is the conclusion of this work and the directions to future developments.

The integration of automation into BIM tools ushers in a new era of possibilities, empowering architects to augment their work, streamline manual tasks, and elevate the quality of their deliverables.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/Wlwr5qBzn0Y>

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